

D5.3

Public acceptance & impact assessment report

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building
trust and sustainability for CCAM

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Contributors

Name	Organisation
Giorgos Zacharopoulos	ICCS
Gorka Vélez	VICOM
Jon Ander Íñiguez de Gordo	VICOM
Ioannis Neokosmidis	INC
Charalampos Kakkavas	INC

Quality Control

	Name	Organisation	Date
Peer review 1	Tobias Mueller	BOSCH	15/12/2025
Peer review 2	Jordi Casademont	i2CAT/UPC	10/12/2025

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ATI	Affinity for Technology Interaction
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
CV	Connected Vehicle
DT	Digital Twin
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
QR	Quick Response (code)
SD	Standard Deviation
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TM	Traffic Management
TMS	Traffic Management System
UC	Use Case
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything (communication)
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the outcomes of Task 5.3, which assessed public acceptance and perceived impact of the PoDIUM platform and associated Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) use cases demonstrated across the three Living Labs in Germany, Spain, and Italy. The study applied a structured evaluation framework derived from Deliverable D5.1, integrating Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) constructs with PoDIUM-specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to trust, usability, usefulness, reliability, privacy, and intention to use.

A total of 135 respondents participated through on-site and online surveys, representing a diverse range of mobility roles (drivers, Vulnerable Road Users - VRUs, operators, public authorities), age groups, and technology backgrounds. Overall, the demographic and Affinity for Technology Interaction (ATI) profiles indicate a sample that is technologically engaged and familiar with mobility innovations, while still reflecting perspectives from non-expert and first-time users.

Across all Living Labs, the results show a strong and consistent positive perception of PoDIUM solutions. KPIs related to Perceived Usefulness and Intention to Use recorded the highest scores, especially in safety-critical urban scenarios (e.g., Ulm and Turin) and cross-border traffic management (Barcelona). Participants recognised the tangible benefits of cooperative manoeuvres, improved VRU protection, tunnel risk management, and enhanced traffic efficiency. Trust levels were also high across all use cases, demonstrating that users felt safe interacting with PoDIUM technologies and confident in the system behaviours demonstrated during the pilots.

At the same time, results highlight areas where expectations must be managed for future deployment. In all Living Labs, Reliability scored lower than Trust, with respondents expressing scepticism that automated or cooperative systems can operate entirely error-free. This “trust-reliability gap” reflects a realistic public understanding of prototype technologies and underlines the need for transparent communication on system limitations and fail-safe mechanisms. Privacy concerns also emerged as a moderate barrier, with a subset of participants expressing reluctance to disclose personal or location data required for cooperative services.

The impact assessment complements these findings by demonstrating the potential value of PoDIUM’s Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) from operational, societal, and technological perspectives. The combination of user perceptions and proof-of-value results provides actionable insights to inform further research, standardisation efforts (WP7), and business model development (WP6).

Overall, the results indicate clear public support for CCAM technologies enabled by multi-connectivity, cooperative perception, and edge-assisted PDI. While challenges remain, particularly around reliability expectations, data governance, and interface usability, the pilots show strong readiness for further deployment, scaling, and integration into real-world mobility systems.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project introduction

PoDIUM supports advanced Use Cases (UCs) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs (LLs) in Germany, Italy, and Spain, PoDIUM tackles all the different requirements for the availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The developed UCs advanced a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital parts of the Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) platform. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions were pursued:

1. A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability, and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
2. Advanced data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards Digital Twins (DTs).
3. Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced CCAM use cases.
4. Ensure software integrity, trust, and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange, and their processing.
5. Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with the integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

This deliverable consolidates the results of the public acceptance survey and the impact assessment. It provides evidence on the perceived value, usability, and adoption potential of PoDIUM solutions, supporting subsequent work in WP6 (business models) and WP7 (standardisation and exploitation).

1.3. Intended audience

The deliverable is classified as “Public”, as a result it will be uploaded to the PoDIUM website, and it will become available to everyone. The main deliverable’s target audiences are:

- Podium Consortium Partners
- European Commission and project reviewers
- Relevant stakeholders in the transport, mobility, and urban planning sectors
- General Public

1.4. Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is structured to provide a clear and coherent overview of the public acceptance and impact assessment activities carried out within the PoDIUM project. It follows the logical flow of the evaluation work in Task 5.3, from the conceptual background and methodological framework to the empirical findings and final interpretation.

Section 2 – Methodology

This section presents the methodological approach used to assess public acceptance and perceived impacts. It builds on the evaluation framework defined in D5.1 and explains the conceptual basis, Key Performance Indicator (KPI) categories, survey design, sampling strategy, data collection process, and analytical methods.

Section 3 – Survey Implementation and Respondent Overview

This section describes how the surveys were deployed across the three Living Labs (Germany, Italy, Spain), including the operational context, dissemination channels, response rates, and demographic characteristics of participants. It provides the empirical foundation for the analysis of user perceptions.

Section 4 – Results of the Public Acceptance Assessment

This section reports the quantitative results for each Living Lab. It includes KPI-level findings for the items listed and defined in D5.1 (Intention to Use, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, Trust, Reliability, Privacy, and Social Norm). Comparative insights across Living Labs are also discussed to highlight similarities, differences, and contextual factors influencing acceptance.

Section 5 – Impact Assessment and Proof of Value

This section presents the broader impact assessment conducted by INC, summarising the value proposition of PoDIUM's Physical and Digital Infrastructure, key technological and societal benefits, and proof-of-value outcomes across the three Living Labs. It complements the public acceptance results by linking user perceptions to system-level performance and expected societal impacts.

Section 6 – Conclusions and Recommendations

This section synthesises the findings of the assessment and provides recommendations for future deployment, standardisation, and exploitation activities. It identifies success factors, barriers to adoption, and implications for large-scale CCAM rollout in line with PoDIUM objectives.

1.5. Relation to WP5 and the PoDIUM project goals

Task 5.3 (of which D5.3 is derived from), builds on demonstration results from Tasks 5.1 (Evaluation methodology and plan) and 5.2 (UCs technical evaluation and LL demonstration activities), linking technical evaluation with societal impact assessment to validate the overall PoDIUM approach.

The methodological approach applied in this deliverable builds directly on the foundations established in Deliverable D5.1 (PoDIUM Evaluation Methodology). While D5.1 defined the overall evaluation framework for WP5 over both technical and user acceptance dimensions, D5.3 operationalises and implements the user acceptance component in real demonstration settings. D5.1 provided the conceptual basis through the adapted Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and identified the key perception-related KPIs (Usefulness, Trust, Reliability, Ease of Use, Intention to Use, and Social Norm). The present deliverable applies this framework to empirical data collected from participants across the three Living Labs, transforming theoretical constructs into measurable outcomes that reflect actual public attitudes toward PoDIUM solutions. This ensures methodological consistency across WP5 while providing a validated bridge between design-phase evaluation planning and implementation-phase assessment.

2. Methodology

This section outlines the methodological approach applied to assess public acceptance and perceived impact of the PoDIUM platform and use cases. It builds upon the user acceptance framework initially defined in Deliverable D5.1 (“PoDIUM Evaluation Methodology”) and materialises it during the demonstration activities carried out in the three project Living Labs (Germany, Spain, Italy).

2.1. Approach and conceptual framework

The evaluation follows a quantitative analysis methods design, combining insights to capture perceptions of safety, trust, usefulness, and overall acceptance of PoDIUM solutions. The conceptual basis draws from the extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) used in D5.1, which incorporates key psychological and behavioural constructs relevant to connected and automated mobility contexts.

In addition to the core TAM variables (Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Trust, Reliability, and Intention to Use), PoDIUM also considers Social Norm as a determinant influencing individual attitudes towards technology adoption (Table 1). This enhancement reflects the social and cooperative dimension of CCAM systems, where user confidence depends not only on personal experience but also on perceptions of collective behaviour and safety assurance. The assessment framework therefore integrates structured surveys capturing numerical trends across user groups and Living Labs.

A key feature of the framework is the diversity of operational conditions across the three PoDIUM Living Labs. Because user perceptions are shaped by the environment in which CCAM technologies are experienced, the evaluation anticipated that certain constructs (particularly Trust and Perceived Usefulness) would vary between controlled highway environments and more complex, mixed-traffic urban settings. Highway demonstrations (e.g., UC5 on the A22 motorway and UC3 on the C-32 corridor) were expected to emphasise reliability, connectivity stability, and continuity of service, while urban demonstrations (e.g., Ulm-UC1, Barcelona-UC2, Turin-UC4) were more likely to affect perceptions of coexistence with VRUs and situational awareness in dynamic environments. Although safety remains a common theme across all Use Cases, the way it is perceived differs depending on context.

PoDIUM’s methodological approach is aligned with established practices in CCAM acceptance research. Similar Horizon projects, such as 5G-MOBIX, SHOW, and C-ROADS, have demonstrated that real-world operating environments strongly influence user trust, perceived usefulness, and adoption intentions. Building on these insights, PoDIUM contributes new evidence on how multi-connectivity, cooperative perception, and edge-enabled services influence public acceptance across diverse contexts.

To ensure a robust evaluation, the framework integrates both technology-oriented and human-centred dimensions of CCAM perception. Insights from behavioural science and transport psychology complement the adapted TAM, recognising that trust in cooperative systems depends on the interplay between human users, digital infrastructure, and automated decision-making. The diversity of Living Lab environments further supports cross-scenario comparison and strengthens the generalisability of findings for future large-scale CCAM deployments.

Table 1: Overview of KPI Categories and Corresponding Indicative Survey Statements

KPI Category	Indicative statements
Intention to use	Assuming I have access to PoDIUM platform, I intend to use it in my daily life.
Perceived Ease of Use	I would find the PoDIUM CAV easy to use in my daily life.
Perceived Usefulness	Using the PoDIUM CAV would increase the travel comfort of disadvantaged people, e.g. elderly.
Perceived System Trust	Overall, I could trust the PoDIUM platform.
Perceived System Reliability	I believe that a PoDIUM CAV is free of errors.
Perceived Privacy Risk	I would feel confident disclosing private information to use the PoDIUM Platform.
Perceived Social Influence (Social Norm)	I would be proud to say that I use a PoDIUM CAV/CV and I would recommend it to people that are close to me

2.2. Survey design and development

Two complementary survey instruments were designed:

- On-site surveys, targeting participants who directly interacted with PoDIUM demonstrations (e.g., drivers, vulnerable road users, operators, and observers).
- Online surveys, disseminated after events to reach broader stakeholder audiences such as public authorities, industry representatives, and members of the wider public.

Both surveys were developed in alignment with the KPI categories defined in Table 1. Question types included multiple-choice items to identify user categories and interaction contexts, and five-point Likert scale statements to measure agreement levels on key acceptance metrics.

Before deployment, the survey underwent a short pilot test with a small group of consortium members and Living Lab representatives. This pre-test ensured clarity, coherence, and technical functionality of the survey. Feedback resulted in minor refinements to wording, response options, and question ordering, improving reliability and ensuring accessibility for users with varying levels of CCAM knowledge.

The final survey followed a structured logic reflecting PoDIUM’s evaluation framework as defined in D5.1. It consisted of four main sections:

- **Demographics and mobility background:** capturing age, gender, user type, mobility role, and prior familiarity with CCAM or C-ITS technologies.
- **Interaction context:** documenting which Use Case the respondent experienced, their mode of participation (e.g., driver, VRU, observer, operator), and the demonstration setting (urban or highway).
- **Perception and acceptance statements:** Likert-scale items aligned with the TAM-based KPI categories:

- Intention to Use
- Perceived Ease of Use
- Perceived Usefulness
- Trust
- Reliability
- Privacy
- Social Norm
- **An example of a typical Likert-scale item was:** “Overall, I could trust the PoDIUM platform.” Responses ranged from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree).
- **Behavioural intention and willingness to adopt:** Capturing respondents’ readiness to use PoDIUM-enabled services in future daily mobility contexts.

The survey was conducted using Microsoft Forms, which provided several advantages for multi-site demonstration campaigns:

- Real-time monitoring of response rates and progress during events
- Built-in data validation to minimise incomplete or invalid submissions
- Consistent survey layout across on-site (QR-coded) and online channels
- Seamless export to Excel, enabling automated descriptive analysis and supporting early data cleaning before consolidation across Living Labs

2.3. Sampling strategy and respondent selection

The sampling approach combined convenience and goal-directed techniques to ensure adequate representation of the key stakeholder groups involved in the PoDIUM demonstrations. Respondents were primarily recruited among participants in the Living Lab events, project partners’ networks, and external stakeholders engaged in related mobility and CCAM initiatives. Efforts were made to include a balanced mix of user profiles, such as CAV passengers, drivers (CV or traditional vehicles), pedestrians/cyclists (VRUs), traffic management operators, and representatives of local administrations.

Although the surveys were not intended to achieve full statistical representativeness, the target of approximately 100 valid responses across the three Living Labs was considered sufficient to support descriptive analysis and cross-site comparison. This sample size enables the identification of broad patterns in public perception while acknowledging that the findings reflect experiential insights rather than population-level estimates.

Clear inclusion criteria were applied to ensure the relevance and validity of participant responses. Eligible respondents were individuals who had directly engaged with the PoDIUM demonstrations, either by participating in the tests (e.g., as drivers, VRUs, passengers or operators) or by observing the scenarios on-site as local residents. Individuals without exposure to the demonstrations or lacking contextual knowledge of the tested use cases were excluded, ensuring that all responses originated from informed interaction with PoDIUM technologies.

2.4. Data collection process and timeline

Surveys were deployed on-site and online during and shortly after demo events.

Timeline:

- April 2025: German Living Lab Demonstration
- October 2025: Italian Living Lab Demonstration
- November 2025: Spanish Living Lab Demonstration & Final Event

Data collection was conducted in parallel with the Living Lab demonstration campaigns:

- April 2025: Initial survey following early pilot activities.
- October 2025: Second wave during extended demonstrations.
- November 2025: Final consolidation survey to capture post-event perceptions.

Participants could complete the survey digitally via QR codes and email links, either after their presence at the demonstration sites or after a presentation given by the Living Labs. Responses were anonymised and stored in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Each Living Lab coordinated local outreach to ensure consistency and maximise engagement.

2.5. Ethical considerations and data protection

All surveys were conducted in accordance with ethical research standards and the principles of informed consent. Participation was entirely voluntary, with respondents informed about the purpose of data collection and their right to withdraw at any time. No personally identifiable information was collected. All data handling followed GDPR-compliant procedures as defined in the project's Data Management Plan. The analysis focused exclusively on aggregated results to ensure participant privacy and confidentiality.

2.6. Data analysis methods

The analysis of survey results was based exclusively on quantitative methods, as the surveys did not include open-ended questions. The dataset consisted of structured responses collected through multiple-choice and 5-point Likert-scale items aligned with the TAM-based KPI categories defined in D5.1. The dataset was processed using a standard statistical tool (Microsoft Excel), following two main analytical steps:

- **Descriptive statistics:** Computation of mode, median, mean, standard deviation and range (max, min) for each question on each KPI category (Intention to Use, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Trust, Reliability, Privacy, and Social Norm).
- **Comparative analysis:** The differences between questions, KPI categories, Living Labs and environments (e.g., urban vs. highway) were studied. This allowed identification of contextual trends, such as variations in ease of use or perceived usefulness scores.

As no open-ended items were included, no qualitative thematic analysis was required. All results were interpreted with reference to the TAM framework and PoDIUM's evaluation objectives, providing evidence on how different aspects of system perception influence acceptance across diverse demonstration environments.

3. Survey Implementation and Respondent Overview

Following the methodological framework established in Chapter 2, the implementation of the public acceptance survey translated the planned approach into concrete data collection activities across the three PoDIUM Living Labs. This chapter describes how the surveys were executed in real demonstration environments, detailing the operational setup, dissemination and outreach strategy, achieved response rates, and participant demographics. The coordinated deployment ensured that comparable and representative insights were gathered from diverse national and use case contexts, forming the empirical foundation for the subsequent analysis of public perception and impact.

3.1. Deployment context within the three Living Labs

The survey campaign was implemented concurrently with the demonstration events conducted across the three PoDIUM Living Labs. Each Living Lab constituted a distinct operational environment, thereby facilitating the collection of diverse insights into user perceptions and attitudes toward Connected and CCAM technologies. The Living Labs provided unique testing conditions, differing not only in geographical and infrastructural characteristics but also in terms of user exposure levels and modes of interaction with the PoDIUM technologies:

- **German Living Lab (Ulm, Germany):** Focused on Urban Mobility and Connected Corridor Management scenarios in the city of Ulm (UC1). The demonstrations evaluated advanced PDI features, multi-connectivity reliability, and a cooperative traffic control scenarios involving private vehicles and VRUs. The scenarios demonstrated included an obstacle that blocks one lane of a two-lane road. Two CAVs (or one CAV and a VRU-cyclist under the 2nd scenario), one from each direction, pass the obstacle with a cooperative manoeuvre.
- **Spanish Living Lab (Barcelona, Spain):** Concentrated on Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) for a User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs in the city of Barcelona (UC2). Also, the Living Lab focused on Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor at C-32 Highway (UC3). The first of the two scenarios demonstrated for UC2 included a firefighter truck which indicated its route to Traffic Management System (TMS), asked for priority signalised crossings, and shared its location at all times, whereas the infrastructure sent warnings to the rest of road users than an emergency vehicle is approaching. As part of the second scenario the infrastructure detected the presence of VRUs and evaluated the potential risks. The infrastructure then sent warnings to the connected VRU about the presence of an emergency vehicle. At the same time, it sent warnings to the vehicles about the presence of VRUs. The UC3 demonstrated scenario included a safety incident within the cross-border area which was managed by a direct-to-vehicle speed/manoeuvre command coming from the PDI.
- **Italian Living Lab (Turin and A22 Motorway):** Addressed trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance within an Urban environment in Turin (UC4) and also focused on Risk Management within a Highway Tunnel in A22 Motorway - Autostrada del Brennero (UC5). For UC4 the demonstrated scenarios included six different sub-scenarios varying from collision avoidance to CAV giving way for VRU with the use of the Trusted Platform Module and the VRU-aware Intersection Movement Assistant (VIMA) application developed as part of the project. For UC5 the demonstrated safety incident scenarios within

Motorway tunnel that included 5 different technical sub-scenarios varying from precise position of CAV within a tunnel, to cooperative adaptive cruise control (CACC) all managed by the Risk Management module developed as part of PoDIUM.

The survey was integrated into the demonstration schedule to capture first-hand impressions from participants directly exposed to PoDIUM solutions. In addition, online participation was enabled to include stakeholders who could not attend on-site demonstrations but had expressed their interest to the project, had relevant domain expertise or were just representatives of the wider public.

By embedding surveys directly within these real-life demonstrations, the evaluation captured immediate user reactions grounded in authentic operational contexts. This approach increased validity and strengthened the reliability of findings derived from the three Living Labs.

To increase the number of responses, the surveys were also conducted through online presentations of the PoDIUM platform with the use of videos either pre-captured for this specific cause or captured during the real-life demonstrations at each Living Lab. The combination of presentations and videos offered the online participants a high-quality perspective on TAM KPIs described at chapter 2.

3.2. Dissemination and outreach channels

A combination of physical and digital dissemination channels was employed to maximise participant engagement and ensure that different stakeholder groups could access the survey.

On-site distribution

During the demonstration events, QR codes linking directly to the Microsoft Forms survey were displayed on slides, badges, yellow vests, roll-up banners, and information stands at the demo locations. In some cases, facilitators also approached participants immediately after the scenarios, briefly explaining the purpose of the survey and inviting them to scan the QR code using their smartphones.

Online distribution

To complement on-site collection, the survey link was disseminated through project partner mailing lists, PoDIUM-related newsletters and institutional websites. Living Lab partners additionally promoted the survey through follow-up emails to event registrants and stakeholders who had attended technical workshops or online presentations. This helped reach participants who could not be present during the live demonstrations but were familiar with the project's objectives and use cases. Online distribution was also used when connectivity or device availability was limited during the on-site demonstrations.

Stakeholder engagement

Targeted outreach was carried out in collaboration with local authorities, road operators, research institutions and industrial partners. These organisations circulated the survey within their networks, enabling the inclusion of traffic management professionals, mobility planners, CCAM experts and representatives of user associations alongside general citizens. Where possible, the survey was presented briefly during meetings or webinars, with a short explanation of how the results would feed into PoDIUM's impact assessment.

Lessons learnt

Across the three Living Labs, it was observed that many on-site attendees were not immediately inclined to complete the survey, mainly due to time constraints, or the perception that the survey would be lengthy. Active encouragement by demonstration staff, clear communication that the survey required less than 10 minutes, and the option to answer later via the online link were important to increase participation. These experiences underline the need for simple, well-signposted survey access and dedicated time slots within demonstration programmes when planning user acceptance studies in future CCAM projects.

3.3. Response rate and sample size

Across all Living Labs, the combined survey campaign aimed for approximately 100 valid responses. While the objective was not to achieve full statistical representativeness, the collected data provided a solid empirical foundation for descriptive and comparative analysis. The response rates achieved reflect a strong level of engagement from participants directly involved in demonstrations.

Table 2: Number of responses and response rate per LL

Living Lab	Location / Type	Valid Responses	Approx. Response Rate
German (Ulm)	Urban scenarios	26	75%
Spanish (Barcelona - C32)	Highway & Urban scenarios	77	85%
Italian (Turin/A22)	Highway & Urban scenarios	32	71%
Total	-	135	77%

Participants in general needed to be persuaded about completing the survey. Despite that, the high on-site response rate demonstrates the advantage of coupling the survey with live demonstrations, where users could form immediate impressions of system usability and safety.

3.4. Demographics and participant characteristics

The respondent pool reflected the diverse stakeholder landscape relevant to CCAM deployments. A total of 135 individuals contributed to the survey across the three Living Labs, representing a mixture of end users, professional stakeholders, and institutional roles.

3.4.1. Demographics

User Roles and Mobility Profiles

Participants included VRUs such as pedestrians and cyclists, private drivers, commercial/logistics operators, traffic management personnel, and representatives of local administrations. Because respondents could select multiple mobility roles, several reported involvements in more than one category (e.g., both driver and VRU). This diversity enables comparisons between experiential user groups and professional stakeholders, supporting PoDIUM's objective of assessing multi-actor acceptance.

Age and Gender Distribution

The sample included participants across all major adult age groups. The largest segments were 26-35 years (31%), 46-55 years (27%), and 36-45 years (24%), with 16% above 55 years. Gender distribution reflected existing patterns in transport and technology participation, with 80% male, 19% female, and a small percentage identifying as non-binary or preferring not to say.

Education and CCAM Background

Most respondents held higher education degrees: 53% university, 25% postgraduate, and 21% doctorate, indicating a relatively well-educated sample.

Regarding familiarity with CCAM and C-ITS systems, levels varied considerably:

- 47% reported adequate knowledge,
- 27% expert-level familiarity,
- 26% had basic to no prior exposure.

This mix is beneficial for analysis, as it allows interpretation of acceptance patterns across both informed stakeholders and first-time users. Also, 64% of participants answered that they have had an autonomous driving experience which demonstrates familiarity with the wider CCAM environment.

Vehicle Ownership and Mobility Behaviour

A majority of respondents (76%) reported owning a vehicle, while 24% did not. This allows examination of how CCAM perceptions differ between habitual vehicle users and those who rely more on active or public transport modes. Also, 79% of the participants mentioned that in their day-to-day lives drive non-autonomous, non-connected vehicles. As respondents were offered the option to choose more than one response, there was also a 60% of participants who declared that they identify as VRUs as well. Connected Vehicle and Connected-Automated Vehicle owners combined cover a 15% of the respondents.

Table 3: Demographics distribution

Characteristic	Description / Distribution
Total respondents	135
Age group	26-35 (31%), 46-55 (27%), 36-45 (24%), >55 (16%), 18-25 (1%)
Gender	Male (80%), Female (19%), Non-binary (1%), Prefer not to say (1%)
Level of education	University level (53%), Post-graduate (25%), Doctorate (21%), PNTS (1%)
Vehicle ownership	Yes (76%), No (24%)
User role*	Usual Vehicle (79%), VRU (60%), CV (10%), CAV (5%)
Familiarity with CCAM/C-ITS	Adequate (47%), Expert (27%), Basic (16%), Limited (8%), None (2%)
Autonomous driving experience	Yes (64%), No (36%)

*Option for more than one answer was offered.

3.4.2. Affinity for Technology Interaction (ATI) Analysis

To complement standard demographics, the survey included the Affinity for Technology Interaction (ATI) scale to assess respondents' predisposition towards engaging with technical systems. ATI is an

established research tool in human technology interaction and helps contextualise trust and ease-of-use perceptions. Across the nine ATI items, responses showed a clear trend towards high technological openness:

High Engagement with Technology

A large proportion of respondents enjoy (percentage of participants selecting either Strongly Agree or Agree) interacting with technical systems:

- 81% like dealing with technical systems in detail
- 87% enjoy testing new technical functions
- 81% try to understand how a system exactly works
- 77% say they attempt to use a system’s full capabilities

These patterns indicate generally tech-positive participants, which is typical of Living Lab audiences involving pilots, demonstrations, and professional stakeholders.

Explorative User Types

Two notable types of responses highlighted the explorative nature of the participants:

- 58% disagreed with the statement “It is enough for me that a system works; I don’t care how or why.” This shows a strong inclination toward understanding system logic, relevant for technologies involving cooperative perception or automation transparency.
- Moreover, 49% disagreed (and strongly disagreed) to the statement that “It is enough for me to know the basic functions.” This suggests that participants do not function only within the pragmatic/basic spectrum but prefer to explore further and as much as possible a technical system.

Implications for PoDIUM Acceptance

The overall high ATI scores help contextualise several observations in Chapter 4:

- Users with high technological affinity tend to rate Perceived Ease of Use and Trust more positively.
- The ATI distribution helps explain why novel CCAM interactions (e.g., via VRU apps or cooperative manoeuvres) were generally well-received.
- However, higher ATI often correlates with higher expectations for system reliability, which aligns with observed scepticism regarding “error-free” operation.

Table 4: Affinity for Technology Interaction responses by percentage

ATI Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I like to occupy myself in greater detail with technical systems	29%	52%	18%	1%	0%
I like testing the functions of new technical systems	34%	53%	13%	0%	0%
I predominantly deal with technical systems because I must.	15%	34%	33%	16%	3%

When I have a new technical system in front of me, I try it out intensively	22%	45%	29%	4%	0%
I enjoy spending time becoming acquainted with a new technical system	27%	53%	16%	4%	0%
It is enough for me that a technical system works; I don't care how or why	2%	12%	19%	58%	9%
I try to understand how a technical system exactly works	23%	59%	11%	7%	0%
It is enough for me to know the basic functions of a technical system	1%	22%	28%	40%	9%
I try to make full use of the capabilities of a technical system	26%	51%	16%	7%	0%

3.4.3. Summary Interpretation

The demographic composition spanning different age groups, user roles, and technology backgrounds, provides a robust basis for interpreting public acceptance patterns. The combination of the list below supports nuanced analysis across different stakeholder perspectives:

- high educational attainment,
- broad mobility roles,
- varied CCAM familiarity, and
- overall strong technological affinity

This diversity also aligns with PoDIUM’s inclusiveness goals, ensuring that findings reflect both general users and expert audiences exposed to CCAM technologies in real operational contexts. The next chapter builds on this demographic and ATI profile to analyse perceptions of usefulness, trust, reliability and behavioural intention across the three Living Labs.

4. Results of the Public Acceptance Assessment

This section details the findings from the PODIUM public acceptance surveys conducted across the three Living Labs. The analysis is structured in two parts. First, an individual assessment of each Living Lab, presenting key descriptive statistics for every question: specifically, the mode, median, mean, standard deviation (SD), and range (min/max). Subsequently, a comparative analysis is performed across the three sites to synthesise broader insights and identify common trends.

4.1. German LL results

4.1.1. Intention to use

The Intention to Use KPI was assessed with two questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 5. The mean value of the two questions is 4.00 with a standard deviation of 0.73.

Table 5: German LL survey results of Intention to Use KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
Assuming I have access to PoDIUM services, I intend to use it in my daily life	4	4	4.08	0.70	5	3
If available, I am planning to use the PoDIUM services	4	4	3.92	0.76	5	2

4.1.2. Perceived ease of use

The Perceived Ease of use KPI was assessed with one question answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 6.

Table 6: German LL survey results of Perceived Ease of Use KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I would find the PoDIUM CAV easy to use in my daily life	4	4	3.76	0.78	5	2

4.1.3. Perceived usefulness

The Perceived Usefulness KPI was assessed with three questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 7. The mean value of the three questions is 4.27 with a standard deviation of 0.72.

Table 7: German LL survey results of Perceived Usefulness KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I would find the PoDIUM CAV useful in my daily life/work	4	4	4.04	0.79	5	3

Using the PoDIUM CAV in my daily life would increase my travel comfort	4	4	4.28	0.61	5	3
Using the PoDIUM CAV would increase the travel comfort of disadvantaged people, e.g. elderly	5	5	4.48	0.77	5	3

4.1.4. Trust

The Trust KPI was assessed with four questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 8. The mean value of the four questions is 3.99 with a standard deviation of 0.57.

Table 8: German LL survey results of Trust KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
Overall, I could trust the PoDIUM services	4	4	3.84	0.69	5	3
During the test I trusted the CCAM service provided by PoDIUM	4	4	3.96	0.61	5	3
I believe that I could trust and rely on PoDIUM CAVs	4	4	4.04	0.45	5	3
As an observer I would feel safe to participate or be around this cooperative manoeuvre in my day-to-day life	4	4	4.12	0.53	5	3

4.1.5. Reliability

The Reliability KPI was assessed with two questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 9. The mean value of the two questions is 3.08 with a standard deviation of 0.83.

Table 9: German LL survey results of Reliability KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I believe that the PoDIUM services will perform consistently under a variety of circumstances and use cases	4	4	3.60	0.71	5	2
I believe that the PoDIUM system that uses a CAV, is free of errors	3	3	2.56	0.96	5	1

4.1.6. Privacy

The Privacy KPI was assessed with two questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 10. The mean value of the two questions is 3.32 with a standard deviation of 1.04.

Table 10: German LL survey results of Privacy KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I would feel confident disclosing private information to use the PoDIUM services	4	3	3.20	1.04	5	1
Using the PoDIUM services does not require private information disclosure	3	3	3.44	1.04	5	2

4.1.7. Social Norm

The Social Norm KPI was assessed with two questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 11. The mean value of the two questions is 3.74 with a standard deviation of 0.71.

Table 11: German LL survey results of Social Norm KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
People whose opinions are important to me would also like the PoDIUM CAV	4	4	3.64	0.57	5	3
I would be proud to say that I use a PoDIUM CAV/CV and I would recommend it to people that are close to me	4	4	3.84	0.85	5	2

4.1.8. Discussion

The assessment of user acceptance within the German Living Lab reveals a generally positive reception towards the PoDIUM cooperative services. The Intention to Use (Mean = 4.00, SD = 0.73) indicates a strong willingness among participants to integrate CCAM solutions into their daily mobility routines.

This intention appears to be primarily driven by Perceived Usefulness (Mean = 4.27, SD = 0.72), which scored the highest among all assessed KPIs (see Figure 1). Notably, the specific item regarding the benefits for disadvantaged groups (e.g., the elderly) achieved the highest individual score in the entire survey (Mean = 4.48, SD = 0.77). This suggests that the societal value proposition of PDI-supported automation, specifically its ability to democratise mobility and enhance safety in complex scenarios such as those from UC1, is a more significant driver of adoption than personal convenience alone.

Figure 1: Mean values of public acceptance KPIs in the German LL survey

While Perceived Ease of Use was rated positively (Mean = 3.76, SD = 0.78), it scored slightly lower than usefulness. This is consistent with the introduction of novel technologies where users anticipate a learning curve regarding the interaction with cooperative infrastructure and automated systems.

A critical finding in this study is the divergence between Trust and Perceived Reliability. Participants reported high levels of trust in the system (Mean = 3.99, SD = 0.57), explicitly stating they felt safe participating in the cooperative manoeuvres. This suggests that the UC1 was successful in conveying a sense of safety and competence.

However, this high trust contrasts with the Reliability KPI, which received the lowest scores (Mean = 3.08, SD = 0.83). Specifically, the item assessing whether the system is "free of errors" received a mean score of only 2.56.

This creates a "pragmatic trust" paradox:

- **Realistic Expectations:** Users do not expect the technology to be infallible. The low score on "error-free" operation indicates a realistic public understanding that complex PDI and connectivity solutions are susceptible to technical faults.
- **Resilience over Perfection:** The fact that Trust remains high despite low Perceived Reliability suggests that users trust the system's fail-safes or the overall safety net provided by the infrastructure, even if they anticipate occasional glitches. They view the system as "safe enough" to use, even if not technically perfect.

The Privacy KPI (Mean = 3.32, SD = 1.04) represents a moderate barrier to acceptance. The scores indicate a hesitancy regarding the disclosure of private information required to enable Vehicle to Everything (V2X) connectivity. In the context of the PoDIUM architecture, where data management is hybrid and distributed, this highlights the necessity for transparent communication regarding data anonymization. For cooperative planners to function effectively, they require granular data from vehicles; however, the results imply that users need greater assurance that this data exchange will not compromise personal privacy.

The Social Norm results (Mean = 3.74, SD = 0.71) suggest that CCAM technologies are viewed as socially desirable. The willingness to recommend the system (Mean = 3.84, SD = 0.85) reinforces the findings from the Perceived Usefulness KPI; users perceive the PoDIUM solution not just as a tool for personal transport, but as a modernization of the transport network that their peers would endorse.

4.1.9. Conclusion

In conclusion, the German Living Lab results demonstrate that the PDI and cooperative technologies developed in PoDIUM address a clear user need, particularly regarding travel comfort and inclusivity. The path to higher acceptance levels lies not necessarily in proving the system is flawless (as users are already sceptical of error-free claims), but in reinforcing the Trust and Privacy frameworks. By ensuring that the corridor management approach is transparent regarding data handling, and by maintaining the high safety standards demonstrated in the scenarios, the ecosystem can bridge the gap between "willingness to use" and actual adoption.

4.2. Spanish LL results

4.2.1. Intention to use

The Intention to Use KPI was assessed with one question in UC2 and two questions in UC3. The results are described in Table 12 and Table 13. The mean value of the KPI for UC2 is 3.90 (SD = 0.76), and 3.69 (SD = 0.82) for UC3.

Table 12: Spanish LL UC2 survey results of Intention to Use KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
Assuming I have access to PoDIUM services, I intend to use it in my daily life	4	4	3.90	0.76	5	1

Table 13: Spanish LL UC3 survey results of Intention to Use KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
If available, I could use the cross-border service on a daily, weekly or ad-hoc basis	4	4	3.88	0.84	5	2
As a TM Operator or road authority rep. I would pay for having the PoDIUM service embedded in my TM systems	3	3	3.50	0.79	5	2

4.2.2. Perceived ease of use

The Perceived Ease of Use KPI was assessed with three questions in UC2 and one question in UC3. The results are described in Table 14 and Table 15. The mean value of the KPI for UC2 is 3.56 (SD = 0.74), and 4.12 (SD = 0.69) for UC3.

Table 14: Spanish LL UC2 survey results of Perceived Ease of Use KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I would find the PoDIUM CAV easy to use in my daily life	3	4	3.64	0.73	5	2
During the demo I found it easy to participate as a Vulnerable Road User (VRU) in the PODIUM system	3	3	3.57	0.83	5	1

During the demo I found it easy and safe as an emergency vehicle driver to operate with the PoDIUM system support	3	3	3.45	0.67	5	3
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Table 15: Spanish LL UC3 survey results of Perceived Ease of Use KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I would find the PoDIUM CAV easy to use in my daily life	4	4	4.12	0.69	5	3

4.2.3. Perceived usefulness

The Perceived Usefulness KPI was assessed with five questions in UC2 and four questions in UC3. The results are described in Table 16 and Table 17. The mean value of the KPI for UC2 is 3.75 (SD = 0.68), and 3.99 (SD = 0.68) for UC3.

Table 16: Spanish LL UC2 survey results of Perceived Usefulness KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
During the Demo I found that the CAV suggests a safer behaviour according to my expectations	4	4	3.90	0.66	5	3
Using the PoDIUM CAV in my daily life would increase my travel comfort	4	4	3.88	0.59	5	3
Using the PoDIUM CAV would increase the travel comfort of disadvantaged people, e.g. elderly	4	4	3.98	0.68	5	3
As a TM operator I would say that these PoDIUM services could contribute to improve the traffic efficiency (and or road safety) in the city (TM operator or road authority)	3	3	3.48	0.71	5	2
During the demo (or in general) I think this service could help the EV to reach the emergency location in less time, thus reducing the time responses to the emergency	3	3	3.50	0.74	5	3

Table 17: Spanish LL UC3 survey results of Perceived Usefulness KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
During the Demo I found that the CAV suggests a safer behaviour according to my expectations	4	4	4.03	0.67	5	3

Using the PoDIUM CAV in my daily life would increase my travel comfort	4	4	4.12	0.64	5	3
Using the PoDIUM CAV would increase the travel comfort of disadvantaged people, e.g. elderly	4	4	4.09	0.62	5	3
I believe the PoDIUM platform can help in increasing the safety and reduce traffic incidents and congestion in highways	3	4	3.74	0.79	5	3

4.2.4. Trust

The Trust KPI was assessed with seven questions in UC2 and four questions in UC3. The results are described in Table 18 and Table 19. The mean value of the KPI for UC2 is 3.77 (SD = 0.75), and 3.82 (SD = 0.75) for UC3.

Table 18: Spanish LL UC2 survey results of Trust KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
Overall, I could trust the PoDIUM platform	4	4	3.98	0.78	5	2
During the test I trusted the CCAM service provided by the PoDIUM platform	4	4	4.05	0.76	5	2
As a VRU I feel safe when using the road either as a pedestrian or cyclist, etc.	3	3.5	3.64	0.79	5	2
During the demo I felt confident using an VRU application deployed on top of the PoDIUM platform	3	4	3.67	0.75	5	2
I believe that I could trust and rely on PoDIUM CAVs	4	4	3.64	0.79	5	2
As a resident of Barcelona I would feel safe to be involved or observe this cooperative manoeuvre in my day-to-day life	4	4	3.90	0.69	5	3
As a TM Operator I would feel comfortable to incorporate the PoDIUM services into the existing TM system	3	3	3.50	0.67	5	3

Table 19: Spanish LL UC3 survey results of Trust KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
Overall, I could trust the PoDIUM platform	4	4	3.88	0.77	5	2
During the test I trusted the CCAM service	4	4	4.06	0.74	5	3

provided by the PoDIUM platform						
I believe that I could trust and rely on PoDIUM CAVs	4	4	3.79	0.73	5	2
As a TM Operator I would feel comfortable to incorporate the PoDIUM services into the existing TM system	3	3	3.56	0.75	5	3

4.2.5. Reliability

The Reliability KPI was assessed with two questions in UC2 and UC3. The results are described in Table 20 and Table 21. The mean value of the KPI is 3.40 for both UCs, with a slight difference in SD (0.88 in UC2 and 0.85 in UC3).

Table 20: Spanish LL UC2 survey results of Reliability KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I believe that the PoDIUM platform will perform consistently under a variety of circumstances and use cases	4	4	3.76	0.82	5	2
I believe that a PoDIUM CAV/CV is free of errors	3	3	3.05	0.94	5	1

Table 21: Spanish LL UC3 survey results of Reliability KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I believe that the PoDIUM platform will perform consistently under a variety of circumstances and use cases	4	4	3.76	0.70	5	2
I believe that a PoDIUM CAV/CV is free of errors	2	3	3.03	1.00	5	1

4.2.6. Privacy

The Privacy KPI was assessed with three questions in UC2 and two questions in UC3. The results are described in Table 22 and Table 23. The mean value of the KPI for UC2 is 3.41 (SD = 1.01), and 3.43 (SD = 0.92) for UC3.

Table 22: Spanish LL UC2 survey results of Privacy KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I would feel confident disclosing private information to use the PoDIUM platform	3	3	3.29	1.09	5	1
Using the PoDIUM platform/app does not require private information disclosure	4	4	3.62	0.96	5	1

I would feel confident disclosing private information to use the PoDIUM VRU app	3	3	3.33	0.98	5	1
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Table 23: Spanish LL UC3 survey results of Privacy KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I would feel confident disclosing private information to use the PoDIUM platform	3	3	3.38	1.04	5	1
Using the PoDIUM platform/app does not require private information disclosure	3	3	3.47	0.79	5	2

4.2.7. Social Norm

The Social Norm KPI was assessed with two questions in both UCs. The results are described in Table 24 and Table 25. The mean value of the KPI for UC2 is 3.77 (SD = 0.87), and 3.84 (SD = 0.74) for UC3.

Table 24: Spanish LL UC2 survey results of Social Norm KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
People whose opinions are important to me would also like the PoDIUM CAV/CV	3	4	3.69	0.84	5	2
I would be proud to say that I use a PoDIUM CAV/CV and I would recommend it to people that are close to me	4	4	3.86	0.90	5	1

Table 25: Spanish LL UC2 survey results of Social Norm KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
People whose opinions are important to me would also like the PoDIUM CAV/CV	4	4	3.74	0.71	5	3
I would be proud to say that I use a PoDIUM CAV/CV and I would recommend it to people that are close to me	4	4	3.94	0.78	5	2

4.2.8. Discussion

The assessment of the Spanish LL reveals a generally positive reception of the PDI and CCAM technologies proposed in the PoDIUM project. Across both UC2 (urban) and UC3 (highway), the aggregate results suggest that users recognise the value proposition of connectivity and cooperation enablers. However, the data highlights distinct variations in how these technologies are perceived depending on the operational environment (urban vs. highway), particularly regarding Perceived Ease of Use and Reliability (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Mean values of public acceptance KPIs in the Spanish LL survey

Both use cases demonstrated strong results in Intention to Use and Perceived Usefulness, validating the core hypothesis that PDI-supported integration is desirable for future transport systems. Interestingly, while UC2 (Urban) recorded a slightly higher Intention to Use (Mean = 3.90, SD = 0.76) compared to UC3 (Mean = 3.69, SD = 0.82), it scored lower in Perceived Usefulness. This suggests that while users may find the urban scenarios, specifically the prioritisation of emergency vehicles and VRU protection, highly desirable and necessary for daily life, they may perceive the realisation of these benefits as more complex or less immediate than the highway scenarios.

In contrast, UC3 achieved higher scores in Perceived Usefulness (Mean = 3.99, SD = 0.68), driven by high ratings for travel comfort (Mean = 4.12, SD = 0.64) and support for disadvantaged groups (Mean = 4.09, SD = 0.62). This indicates that the benefits of continuous, resilient service in a cross-border highway context are readily apparent to users, likely due to the tangible impact on reducing congestion and enhancing safety consistency across borders.

A significant divergence was observed in the *Perceived Ease of Use* KPI. UC3 outperformed UC2 significantly in this metric (UC3 Mean = 4.12 vs. UC2 Mean = 3.56). The urban environment of UC2, characterized by complex interactions between emergency vehicles, VRUs, and dynamic traffic flows, likely contributes to a lower perception of ease. The cognitive load required to interact with systems in a dense city centre, even if automated, appears to be higher than that required for highway commuting services. The UC3 scenarios, which focus on smooth traffic management and commuting, present a more streamlined user experience that participants found intuitive. This finding underscores the challenge of designing CCAM interfaces for urban environments where the "chaos" of mixed traffic must be distilled into clear and easy-to-use system responses.

Trust levels were consistent and moderately high across both environments (UC2 Mean = 3.77; UC3 Mean = 3.82), suggesting that the PDI technologies have successfully established a baseline of credibility.

However, *Reliability* emerged as the most significant area of concern for both use cases (Mean = 3.40 for both). Deeper analysis of the individual items reveals that this score is heavily impacted by scepticism regarding the systems' technical perfection. The specific item "I believe that a PoDIUM CAV/CV is free of errors" received the lowest scores in the entire survey (UC2 Mean = 3.05; UC3 Mean = 3.03).

This result is critical; it indicates that while users *trust* the platform generally, they maintain a realistic (and perhaps healthy) scepticism regarding the infallibility of automated systems. This aligns with broader literature on automation, where users are often wary of "glitches" or edge-case failures. For road authorities and operators, this signals that deployment strategies should not promise perfection but rather robust fallback mechanisms and resilience, qualities that users seem to doubt in the current prototype phase.

Privacy scores remained moderate (UC2 Mean = 3.41; UC3 Mean = 3.43), lagging behind other KPIs like Social Norm and Usefulness. The variation in responses (SD > 1.0 for several privacy questions) indicates a polarized user base; some users are comfortable disclosing data for improved services, while a significant minority retains strong reservations.

Given that UC3 relies on cross-border data exchange, the fact that its privacy score was not significantly lower than the domestic UC2 result is a positive indicator for the feasibility of interoperable data management environments. However, the relatively low mean suggests that transparency regarding data usage remains a prerequisite for widespread adoption.

4.2.9. Conclusion

The results from the Spanish LL illustrate a promising landscape for PoDIUM technologies. The high *Intention to Use* in Barcelona (UC2) highlights a market demand for safety-critical urban PDI services, despite the user interface challenges inherent in complex city environments. Conversely, the high *Ease of Use* and *Usefulness* ratings in the cross-border corridor (UC3) validate the effectiveness of PDI in streamlining highway traffic management. Moving forward, bridging the gap between "general trust" and "perceived reliability" will be key. Addressing user scepticism about system errors and further assuring data privacy will be essential steps in transitioning these solutions from Living Labs to real-world deployment.

4.3. Italian LL results

4.3.1. Intention to use

The Intention to Use KPI was assessed with two questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning "strongly disagree" and 5 "strongly agree". The results are described in Table 26. The mean value of the two questions is 4.06 with a standard deviation of 0.53.

Table 26: Italian LL survey results of Intention to Use KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
Assuming I have access to PoDIUM services, I intend to use it in my daily life	4	4	4.16	0.58	5	3
If available, I am planning to use the PoDIUM services	4	4	3.97	0.48	5	3

4.3.2. Perceived ease of use

The Perceived Ease of Use KPI was assessed with one question answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 27.

Table 27: Italian LL survey results of Intention to Use KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
During the demo I found it easy to participate as a VRU in the PODIUM system by using the relevant app	3	3	3.55	0.72	5	3

4.3.3. Perceived usefulness

The Perceived Usefulness KPI was assessed with four questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 28. The mean value of the two questions is 4.06 with a standard deviation of 0.64.

Table 28: Italian LL survey results of Perceived Usefulness KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I would find the PoDIUM CAV useful in my daily life/work	4	4	4.06	0.73	5	3
During the Demo I found that the CAV suggests a safer behaviour according to my expectations	4	4	3.90	0.47	5	3
Using the PoDIUM CAV in my daily life would increase my travel comfort	4	4	4.19	0.65	5	3
Using the PoDIUM CAV would increase the travel comfort of disadvantaged people, e.g. elderly	4	4	4.10	0.70	5	3

4.3.4. Trust

The Trust KPI was assessed with five questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 29. The mean value of the five questions is 3.94 with a standard deviation of 0.62.

Table 29: Italian LL survey results of Trust KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
Overall, I could trust the PoDIUM services	4	4	3.97	0.66	5	2
During the test I trusted the CCAM service provided by PoDIUM	4	4	4.00	0.52	5	3
I believe that I could trust and rely on	4	4	4.13	0.50	5	3

PoDIUM CAVs						
As a Traffic Management Operator I would feel comfortable to incorporate the PoDIUM services into the existing TM system	4	4	3.84	0.69	5	3
As a local resident of Torino I would feel safe to be involved or observe this CAV operation in my day-to-day life	4	4	3.77	0.72	5	3

4.3.5. Reliability

The Trust KPI was assessed with two questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 30. The mean value of the two questions is 3.48 with a standard deviation of 0.63.

Table 30: Italian LL survey results of Reliability KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I believe that the PoDIUM services will perform consistently under a variety of circumstances and use cases	4	4	4.06	0.51	5	3
I believe that a PoDIUM CAV is free of errors	3	3	2.90	0.75	4	1

4.3.6. Privacy

The Privacy KPI was assessed with two questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 31. The mean value of the two questions is 3.56 with a standard deviation of 0.78.

Table 31: Italian LL survey results of Privacy KPI (5-point Likert scale)

I would feel confident disclosing private information to use the PoDIUM VRU app	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
I would feel confident disclosing private information to use the PoDIUM VRU app	4	4	3.77	0.84	5	2
Using the PoDIUM services does not require private information disclosure	3	3	3.35	0.71	5	2

4.3.7. Social Norm

The Social Norm KPI was assessed with two questions answered using a 5-point Likert scale, 1 meaning “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. The results are described in Table 32. The mean value of the two questions is 3.74 with a standard deviation of 0.60.

Table 32: Italian LL survey results of Social Norm KPI (5-point Likert scale)

Question	Mode	Median	Mean	SD	Max	Min
People whose opinions are important to me would also like the PoDIUM CAV	4	4	3.65	0.61	5	3
I would be proud to say that I use a PoDIUM CAV/CV and I would recommend it to people that are close to me	4	4	3.84	0.58	5	3

4.3.8. Discussion

The evaluation of the Italian Living Lab, covering Use Case 4 (Urban Intersections) and Use Case 5 (Tunnel Safety), demonstrates a robust user endorsement of the proposed technologies (see Figure 3). The Intention to Use (Mean = 4.06) is particularly high, suggesting that users are ready to adopt PoDIUM services for both cooperative intersection management and GNSS-denied tunnel guidance.

Figure 3: Mean values of public acceptance KPIs in the Italian LL survey

This positive intention is strongly correlated with Perceived Usefulness (Mean = 4.06, SD = 0.64). Similar to the other Living Lab findings, the societal dimension plays a crucial role here. The highest-rated items within this category relate to increasing travel comfort (Mean = 4.19, SD = 0.65) and improving mobility for disadvantaged groups (Mean = 4.10, SD = 0.70). This indicates that the value of the Italian Living Lab's solutions is perceived not just in terms of technical traffic efficiency, but as a tool for inclusive mobility and enhanced safety for Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs).

Perceived Ease of Use (Mean = 3.55, SD = 0.72) received a moderate score. Since this KPI specifically assessed the user interface employed in the urban intersection scenario, the score suggests that while the interaction is manageable, the interface requires further refinement to match the seamless experience expected from driver assistance/information systems.

The Italian Living Lab data presents an interesting insight regarding user trust. The overall Trust score is high (Mean = 3.94, SD = 0.62), with participants notably stating they could "rely on PoDIUM CAVs" (Mean = 4.13, SD = 0.50). This trust appears resilient even in the challenging environment of a tunnel (UC5) or complex intersections (UC4).

However, an analysis of the Reliability KPI reveals a dichotomy. While users rated the system's ability to "perform consistently under a variety of circumstances" very high (Mean = 4.06, SD = 0.51), they gave the lowest score of the entire survey to the assertion that the system is "free of errors" (Mean = 2.90, SD = 0.75). This reveals a "Robustness Paradox" aligned with the German and Spanish findings:

- **Tolerance for Imperfection:** Users clearly distinguish between bugs (errors) and failure. They accept that the software may have minor errors (low score on "free of errors") but are simultaneously convinced that the service will remain operational and consistent (high score on "consistency").
- **Operational Confidence:** Unlike a fragile system where one error leads to a crash, users perceive the PoDIUM ecosystem as robust. They trust the system to deliver valid movement suggestions and positioning data (tunnel/intersection) consistently, even if they assume the underlying technology is not perfect.

The Privacy KPI (Mean = 3.56, SD = 0.78) indicates a cautious but generally open attitude. Interestingly, participants reported a relatively high confidence in disclosing private information (Mean = 3.77, SD = 0.84), which is higher than the perceived lack of requirement for disclosure (Mean = 3.35, SD = 0.71). This suggests that users in the Italian Living Lab understand that services like "movement suggestions" and "tunnel positioning" inherently require data exchange. They appear willing to trade some privacy for the specific safety benefits offered by UC4 and UC5, provided the context (safety/efficiency) justifies it.

The Social Norm results (Mean = 3.74, SD = 0.60) align with the other positive indicators. The willingness to recommend the system (Mean = 3.84, SD = 0.58) suggests that the integration of infrastructure sensing and CAV manoeuvres is seen as a progressive step for the city of Turin and its transport network. The validation from "people whose opinions are important to me" implies that smart infrastructure is becoming a socially expected standard for modern urban planning.

4.3.9. Conclusion

In conclusion, the results from the Italian Living Lab validate the multi-connectivity and cooperative perception approaches applied in urban and tunnel environments. The data highlights a sophisticated user base that prioritizes consistency and societal benefit over technical perfection. Users are willing to rely on the system and share necessary data, provided the system delivers tangible safety improvements for VRUs and reliable guidance in critical zones like tunnels. Future development should focus on improving the usability of the end-user applications (Ease of Use) to match the high levels of trust placed in the backend infrastructure.

4.4. Comparison between Living Lab results

4.4.1. Overview

The deployment of PoDIUM technologies across three diverse national contexts, Germany (UC1), Spain (UC2, UC3), and Italy (UC4, UC5), provides a comprehensive set of data for evaluating the acceptance of PDI solutions. By contrasting urban environments (Ulm, Barcelona, Turin) with highway environments (Barcelona's C-32 highway, Brennero tunnel), distinct patterns emerge regarding user perception.

Overall, the aggregate results indicate a positive reception of the proposed PDI functionalities, with Intention to Use and Perceived Usefulness scoring consistently high across all pilot sites (see Figure 4). However, variations in Perceived Ease of Use and Reliability suggest that the operational domain significantly influences user confidence, with notable distinctions even among the urban use cases.

Figure 4: Comparison of mean KPI results across UCs

4.4.2. Perceived Usefulness and Intention to Use

Across the three Living Labs, the perceived utility of the systems was the strongest driver of acceptance, particularly in urban settings where interaction complexity is higher.

- Urban Safety and Criticality:** The highest Perceived Usefulness score was observed in the German Living Lab (UC1: M=4.27), located in the city of Ulm. This suggests that users perceive the immediate value of cooperative manoeuvres in urban safety-critical scenarios, specifically obstacle avoidance on obstructed lanes, more acutely than broader traffic optimization. Similarly, the Italian Urban site (UC4: M=4.04) in Turin scored highly, reinforcing the hypothesis that systems actively protecting Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) at urban intersections generate the strongest "buy-in" from participants.
- Traffic Management Scenarios:** While still positive, the scores for UC2 (Barcelona Urban Traffic Flow) and UC5 (Highway Tunnel Risk Management) were slightly lower (M=3.75 and M=3.84, respectively). This indicates that while users value systemic efficiency and risk management, the perceived personal benefit is marginally lower than in scenarios involving direct collision avoidance or specific cooperative manoeuvres.

Intention to Use remained robust across the board, with the German UC1 (M=4.00) and Spanish UC2 (M=3.90) leading. This confirms that despite the varying complexity of the use cases, the demand for PDI-enabled safety and efficiency services is uniform across European contexts.

4.4.3. The Impact of Environment on Ease of Use

A significant divergence appears when analysing Perceived Ease of Use, highlighting the difference between specific highway environments and complex urban centres.

- The Highway Advantage:** The Spanish UC3 recorded the highest Ease of Use score (M=4.12). This can be attributed to the nature of the use case: highway traffic management and

commuting services generally require less cognitive load and complex interaction from the driver compared to urban navigation.

- The Urban Variance: Among the urban use cases, there is notable variation. The Spanish UC2 (Barcelona) recorded the lowest Ease of Use score (M=3.56), likely due to the high density and complexity of the Barcelona city centre involving interactions with emergency vehicles and dynamic signalling. In contrast, the German UC1 (Ulm) and Italian UC4 (Turin) scored higher (M=3.76 and M=3.74, respectively). This suggests that "Urban" is not a monolith; specific cooperative manoeuvres (like the one in Ulm) may be perceived as easier to manage than the broader, multi-actor traffic flow optimization tested in Barcelona.

4.4.4. The Trust-Reliability Paradox

A consistent trend across all three Living Labs is the gap between Trust and Reliability.

- Trust: Participants expressed a generally high level of trust in the PDI concepts and the institutions managing them (scores ranging from ~3.77 to 3.99). The German LL (UC1) led this category, suggesting high confidence in cooperative automated manoeuvres within the urban environment of Ulm.
- Reliability: In contrast, Reliability was the lowest-scoring KPI across every single use case (range: 3.08 to 3.60). The German LL (UC1) and Spanish LL (UC2, UC3) mostly scored around the neutral mark.

This dichotomy suggests that while users trust the intent of the system and feel safe during the demonstrations, they remain sceptical about the technical maturity of the solution. The specific survey items regarding systems being "free of errors" consistently pulled these averages down. This indicates a realistic user understanding that PDI technologies, while promising, are still in a prototype phase and must demonstrate higher robustness before commercial deployment.

4.4.5. Privacy and Social Norms

Privacy concerns were relatively uniform across the pilot sites, generally scoring as the second-lowest KPI (range: 3.32 to 3.55). The standard deviations for privacy were notably high (e.g., SD > 1.0 in several instances), indicating a polarised user base. There was no significant difference between the cross-border scenario (UC3) and the urban scenarios (UC1, UC2, UC4), suggesting that the nature of data sharing (vehicle to infrastructure) is the primary concern, rather than the geographical scope or the density of the environment.

Finally, Social Norm scores were consistent (range: 3.72 to 3.86), implying that users believe their peers would support the adoption of these technologies, regardless of whether the implementation is in Germany, Spain, or Italy.

4.4.6. Conclusions and recommendations

The comparative analysis of the PoDIUM Living Labs validates the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) for PDI-enabled CCAM services, confirming that while users in Germany, Spain, and Italy recognise the high utility of these systems, specific barriers to adoption remain. The results highlight a clear distinction between the strong market demand for safety-critical interventions (Urban Intersections and Obstacle Avoidance) and the cognitive challenges posed by complex, multi-modal urban traffic management.

Based on these cross-site findings, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the future deployment and acceptance of PDI technologies:

1. **Prioritize Resilience over Perfection:** The consistent "Trust-Reliability Gap" indicates that users are sceptical of "error-free" claims. Road authorities and operators should shift their communication strategy to emphasise **resilience and fail-safe mechanisms** rather than technical infallibility. Demonstrating how the PDI infrastructure handles anomalies or connectivity loss will be more effective in building long-term trust than promising a flawless system.
2. **Simplify the Urban Interface:** The lower *Ease of Use* scores in the complex Barcelona environment (UC2) suggest that current interfaces for urban traffic management may be overwhelming. Developers should focus on reducing the cognitive load for drivers and operators in dense city centres, perhaps by filtering information more aggressively and presenting only the most actionable data during critical manoeuvres.
3. **Harmonise Data Privacy Frameworks:** With privacy scores consistently lagging behind usefulness, and high standard deviations indicating user polarisation, a transparent, EU-wide standard for PDI data handling is essential. To support cross-border scenarios (like UC3), users must be assured that their vehicle data is treated with the same rigorous standards regardless of which national infrastructure they are connected to.
4. **Leverage Social Proof:** The high *Social Norm* scores suggest that peer influence is a powerful tool. Early adopters and pilot participants are likely to be effective ambassadors. Future deployment strategies should leverage this by showcasing successful "community" use cases to normalise the technology among the wider public.

5. Impact Assessment and Proof of Value

5.1. Overview of PoDIUM value proposition

PoDIUM project offers a holistic answer to the critical challenges facing the deployment of Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) in Europe. Its value proposition lies in the idea, development and validation of a flexible, interoperable and trustworthy Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) capable to support higher levels of automation and cooperation between vehicles, infrastructures and vulnerable road users. In the broader framework of the project's impact assessment and of the activities towards the validation of its value, PoDIUM proposition represents both a technological and a socioeconomic innovation directly contributing to the policy ambitions of Europe for a safe, resilient and sustainable mobility.

Today, communication and computation architectures are insufficient to meet the performance and trust requirements of next generation mobility. The automotive sector enters an era where connectivity constitutes a significant characteristic. Currently, new vehicles are connected generating huge amount of data in real time. These flows of data will be expanded beyond basic status information to include high-definition sensors data, coordination of cooperative manoeuvres and predictive control inputs. Future communication and computational power requirements will significantly exceed the capabilities of current 4G and early 5G-based Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) networks which were initially designed to mainly support low-bandwidth safety beacons.

PoDIUM addressed this structural challenge through a holistic system architecture that combined multiple-connectivity, distributed computing, edge intelligence and data integrity mechanisms into an integrated PDI. This architecture has been designed to dynamically adapt to service requirements ensuring that all the functions that are more latency-sensitive and safety-critical are processed at the edge of the network, while large volume or non-time-critical tasks are allocated to cloud infrastructures. The proposed three-layer model, that includes road-level systems, edge and network services as well as cloud-based coordination, creates a continuum between physical and digital assets. It also allows the uninterrupted exchange of data among vehicles, roadside units, sensors, traffic management centres and end users, creating thus the basic conditions for cooperative automated mobility.

The value proposition of PoDIUM demonstrates that the combination of multi-connectivity and edge-native computing can guarantee the required latency, reliability and scalability levels for CCAM services. The multi-connectivity framework of PoDIUM integrates multiple radio-access technologies such as 5G, 5G mmWave, LTE, C-V2X (LTE-PC5), ITS-G5 (IEEE 802.11p), Wi-Fi (including 60 GHz) and fibre optics, under a coordinated orchestration mechanism. This setup allows data to flow in heterogeneous networks with redundancy and seamless handover, ensuring service continuity even in complex cross-border environments or in zones with limited coverage. By allowing the parallel and adaptive use of different communication links, PoDIUM created a robust basis for applications ranging from comfort services to mission-critical cooperative perception and manoeuvre coordination.

A key component of PoDIUM's value proposition is the deployment of distributed intelligence at the edge of the network that enables the real-time analytics and the perception close to the point that the data are generated. Through the use of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) technology, environmental perception models and digital twins are implemented at local nodes combining inputs from vehicles, roadside infrastructures and vulnerable road users. Such a distributed processing significantly decreases latency, calms down network congestion and supports the reliable detection

of hazardous events even within milliseconds. By integrating the artificial intelligence and predictive models, PoDIUM extends the situational awareness of both vehicles and traffic operators, enhancing thus safety, traffic efficiency and users experience.

Trust, transparency and cybersecurity represent another central pillar of PoDIUM value proposition.

Public acceptance of connected and automated mobility depends not only on technical performance, but also on the confidence in the integrity of the data and the resilience of the system. PoDIUM addresses such requirements by incorporating Trusted Computing mechanisms into both vehicles and roadside equipment. The adoption of Trusted Platform Modules (TPM) offers a hardware-based root of trust that allows the attestation of software integrity across the entire ecosystem. Complementing this approach, PoDIUM introduces quality indicators which are independent of the implementation of the C-ITS messages. These indicators allow the receivers to evaluate the reliability and the truthfulness of information independently of its source or sensor origin, contributing to the transparent and accountable exchange of data. **This dual focus on technical integrity and trustworthiness of information constitutes a critical factor for the social legitimacy and the regulatory compliance of the future CCAM deployments.**

The proof of value of PoDIUM's innovations is based on the extensive validation in three Living Labs located in Germany, Italy and Spain. These trial sites cover different geographical, regulatory and operational environments, urban centres, highways and cross-border areas, offering a holistic evaluation of platform's efficiency in real conditions. In these Living Labs, PoDIUM demonstrates a series of representative use cases related to the cooperative traffic management, the cross-border service continuity, the control of the multimodal corridors, integrity and truth verification as well as the resilient operation in constrained environments like tunnels. Each use case is defined by measurable KPIs that include latency, reliability, scalability environmental perception accuracy, safety performance and energy efficiency. The trials showed encouraging results for safety critical applications. These results offer clear evidence of the technical and operational feasibility of the proposed system.

Beyond the technical dimension, PoDIUM also proves its **socioeconomic and policy value**. The project demonstrates that a distributed, secure and interoperable infrastructure can unlock new business models and multi-stakeholder value chains that link car manufacturers, road operators, infrastructure providers, service providers and public authorities. Through the technoeconomic analyses, PoDIUM assesses the financial viability of CCAM services supported by edge and cloud infrastructures. This analytical framework offers decision makers quantitative figures for the future return on investment, strengthening thus the case for large-scale deployment.

In policy terms, **the value proposition of PoDIUM is directly aligned with EU objectives for safe, resilient transport and smart mobility** and contributes to the implementation of the European data strategy, the sustainable and smart mobility strategy as well as the European green deal. By supporting efficient and safety-oriented mobility services, PoDIUM architecture addresses the key dimensions of EU agenda for digital transition. In addition, through the active participation in standardization fora and bodies such as ETSI, 3GPP, 5GAA etc., **PoDIUM ensures that its outcomes are consistent with the emerging European and international frameworks for V2X interoperability, security and cross-border service continuity.**

At the societal level, the concept of PoDIUM offers tangible benefits that directly affect public acceptance. By improving the accuracy and the speed of hazard detection and communication, the system enhances road safety and reduces accidents' probability, especially for vulnerable road users like pedestrians and cyclists. Its contribution to the smoother traffic flows and optimized routing

translates into a reduction of traffic congestion, reduced travel times and lower emissions that jointly contribute to environmental sustainability and quality of life. The reliability and transparency ensured through its trust mechanisms enhance citizens confidence in automated systems which is a prerequisite for public acceptance of CCAM technologies.

In conclusion, the value proposition of PoDIUM extends beyond the technical advancement to incorporate system, economic and social transformation. It provides a proven pathway towards an interoperable, trustworthy and sustainable CCAM ecosystem, capable to offer measurable benefits in terms of safety, efficiency and environment. Within the context of the project's impact assessment and proof-of-value activities, PoDIUM demonstrates that the integration of multi-connectivity, edge computing technology and trust-based data management constitute the foundation for a large-scale, citizens-oriented deployment of connected and automated mobility in Europe.

5.2. Identified benefits and added value

PoDIUM delivers clear and measurable benefits for connected, cooperative and automated mobility by combining a flexible physical and digital infrastructure with edge/cloud intelligence and multi-connectivity. In an environment where every new vehicle is connected and the volume of data from vehicles, infrastructures and road users increases drastically, the value of PoDIUM lies in transforming this heterogeneity and scale into safer roads, more efficient operations and a data driven way of mobility management. Its reference architecture covers three layers, systems at the level of the road, multi-access edge computing and cloud, and has been designed to be interoperable with both mobile and short-range technologies. This offers the reliability, the redundancy and the latency guarantees required by the higher-level automation and the advanced V2X use cases, while maintaining in parallel the compatibility to the older versions in the long lifecycle of the vehicles. It is important that PoDIUM applied this architecture in practice in three Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain demonstrating demanding urban, highway and cross-border scenarios under real traffic conditions.

A central element of PoDIUM's added value is road safety improvement, especially for vulnerable road users like pedestrians and cyclists. PoDIUM integrates VRUs in the same cooperative frame as vehicles and infrastructures, overcoming the historic limitation that VRUs rarely use automotive-specific radios. By adopting a multi-connectivity approach, including LTE, 5G cmWave, 5G mmWave hotspots, ITS-G5, Wi-Fi 60 GHz and traditional Wi-Fi, PoDIUM ensures that VRUs can be detected and protected using the channels and the devices they already possess. At the edge, an advanced environmental perception model fuses inputs from connected vehicles, infrastructure nodes and VRUs and scales up to tens of simultaneous contributors. The model is resilient in real-world communication artefacts such duplicates and out of sequence packets and is being enhanced by quality indicators which quantify the truthfulness of each observation. This means that the safety-critical services, like alerts for upcoming collisions or detection of a pedestrian who steps into a crosswalk, are not only fast but also trustworthy. Digital twins at the corridor or intersection level further enhance the protection by predicting the short-term trajectories of all actors and detecting accidents before they materialise. PoDIUM's security stack adds an extra layer of safety using Trusted Platform Modules and remote attestation for the validation of software integrity on vehicles, roadside units and edge nodes, reducing the risk that compromised devices inject misleading messages into safety functions. All these elements are translated into higher VRUs detection rates, lower latency from sensor to road user and more reliable service levels, KPIs that PoDIUM defined and measured in its use cases.

PoDIUM also increases the operational efficiency for the deployment of complex use cases. The traditional approach is to have these computations in a vehicle or not at all. PoDIUM distributes

intelligence across the system: latency and coordination are carried out on the MEC, strategic optimisation and long-term analytics are performed in the cloud, while vehicles and RSUs handle pre-processing and local modelling. This multi-level design reduces transport latency and backhaul load allowing the “ad-hoc road management”, the creation of a managed road part using data from connected road users, even in cases in which no infrastructure sensors are installed. The orchestration is also built in. A cross-operator service orchestrator can request radio and computational resources from multiple mobile network operators and neutral hosts, pool MEC capacity and ensure that the right service is executed with the right priority at the right place. Multipath scheduling in heterogeneous links and carrier aggregation further improves the resilience without bespoke per-use-case engineering, while the extended C-ITS messages (e.g. CPM, CAM, VAM, DENM, MAPEM/SPATEM, IVIM, MCM) provide standardised interfaces for applications logic. As a result, the introduction or scale up of a new function, cooperative lane merging, emergency vehicles priority, management of incidents in tunnels, is a topic of activating and configuring reusable platform’s capabilities instead of building bespoke vertical stacks. Living Labs act as environments close to the production with automated testing and monitoring, reducing integration cycles and providing early KPIs evidence before wider rollout. For the operators and public authorities, such an efficiency is translated into less truck rolls, faster time-to pilot and a demonstrable path from pilot to scaled development, including cross-border continuity.

Perhaps, the most transformative benefit is that PoDIUM enables data-driven mobility management. Today’s traffic management centres mainly monitor, estimate and react using mainly sparse fixed sensors. They know few about origin-destination patterns in real time and can only indirectly influence the demand. PoDIUM changes the paradigm by turning connected vehicles and VRUs into high-fidelity, privacy-preserving probes and by creating a two-way cooperation between the users of the road network and the infrastructure. The MEC-based digital twin combines static attributes of the road and dynamic, real-time information into an extended local dynamic map, while artificial intelligence services at the edge and in the cloud compute optimal tactical and strategic actions. Since platform knows not only where the vehicles are exactly but also their short-term trajectories and manoeuvre intentions, it can coordinate individual actors at local level and align them to a network level strategy e.g. smoothing flows, reducing hard braking and stop and go waves and reallocating green time precisely when and where it yields the maximum benefit. Emergency vehicle pre-emption and the priority routing, reduces response times without causing congestion. For tunnels and other constrained environments, PoDIUM’s corridor-specific twins support the fast detection of incidents, the accurate counting of vehicles and the controlled metering, improving both the safety and throughput. All of this supported by explicit KPIs, latency budgets from sensors to MEC to road users, service reliability targets, detection and perception times that allow managers to apply, benchmark and constantly improve their services.

Trust and interoperability are integral parts of platform’s added value. Because automotive and communication technologies evolve in different timelines, multiple connectivity approach of PoDIUM maintains service continuity across generations. The extensions of C-ITS messages integrate quality indicators so that receivers to be able to weight information by confidence rather than treating all inputs as equal. Software integrity attestation links messages origin with verifiable software states enabling policies that take action only on data from known-good configurations. These measures in combination with privacy-preserving data handling, make cross-sector data exchange enough to underpin cooperative automation at scale.

The societal and environmental benefits of PoDIUM are also prominent. By coordinating vehicles and protecting vulnerable users of the road network with greater precision, PoDIUM reduces accidents

and make walking and cycling more attractive. By smoothing traffic and routing more intelligently, it cuts wasted time, fuel consumption and emissions. By enabling automation services, like shuttles and shared mobility with robust edge support, PoDIUM succeeds to accelerate the shift to right-sized trips with lower impact. By developing a neutral, aligned to standards platform with open interfaces, it lowers the barriers of SME's and third parties to innovate, catalysing new business models around corridor management, predictive maintenance, localized perception as a service or cross-border logistics orchestration.

In summary, PoDIUM's benefits and added value are systemic. It raises the safety ceiling for everyone on the road, especially vulnerable users, by combining low-latency edge intelligence, multi-connectivity and verifiable data quality. It lowers the operational burden of deploying and running demanding connected and automated mobility use cases through orchestration, reuse and real-world Living Labs. And it equips authorities with a data-driven traffic management capability that sees further, reacts faster and coordinates more fairly, converting the raw scale of connected mobility into measurable improvements in flow, resilience and sustainability. This is how PoDIUM turns the promise of CCAM into deployable, interoperable and trustworthy practice across cities, highways and borders.

5.3. Barriers and challenges to adoption

While PoDIUM successfully validated its architectural and technical objectives in complex LL environments, the transition to widespread commercial and public adoption introduces specific challenges that need to be overcome. This section identifies and discusses the primary barriers to the adoption of PoDIUM solutions.

One of the main challenges for adoption is the difference between rapid technological innovation and the slower pace of regulatory and standardization processes. Current regulations often lag behind cutting-edge developments, unintentionally delaying the deployment of advanced systems. Specifically, some of PoDIUM's most advanced cooperative functions are not fully reflected in existing regulatory frameworks. This creates uncertainty for deployment, particularly in areas like interoperability or legal responsibility. Addressing this requires proactive engagement by both ensuring strict compliance with local authorities and maintaining full awareness and adherence to the evolving EU legal framework, and aligning technical implementations with existing ETSI standards to foster future-proof interoperability and regulatory acceptance. Furthermore, providing evidence from pilots and Living Labs can support future updates to standards and inform policy discussions, helping regulators evolve the framework at a pace that remains compatible with emerging cooperative services.

Closely related to regulation is the issue of privacy, as the PDI architecture handles large volumes of highly sensitive data, including real-time vehicle kinematics, infrastructure video streams used for collective perception, or the precise location of VRUs. One of the deployment's main implications would be the necessity for strict adherence to GDPR and the ethical principles of the EU AI Act. Without guaranteed data minimization and demonstrable technical measures to protect Personally Identifiable Information (PII), public trust could be undermined, leading to rejection of the technology. This must be addressed by ensuring real-time anonymisation of sensor data, such as blurring in Video Analytics processing, processing PII at the MEC layer, and implementing robust privacy-by-design principles across all system components.

Widespread adoption also requires overcoming barriers related to infrastructure readiness and cost considerations. This involves considerable Capital Expenditure (CapEx) to install and maintain dedicated PoDIUM components, including RSUs and MEC servers. The primary implication is that the

high-cost consideration potentially limits initial deployments to government-funded pilots, preventing market scale due to insufficient infrastructure readiness. Road operators will demand a clear, quantified Return on Investment (ROI) that outweighs this high CapEx. This barrier should be addressed by developing comprehensive economic models demonstrating the long-term ROI based on quantified benefits regarding safety, throughput, and environmental gains, and by advocating for public-private partnerships and even modular, phased deployment strategies that employ and upgrade existing roadside infrastructure instead of requiring complete replacement.

User trust is one of the most sensitive non-technical barriers to adoption, largely determined by the perceived reliability of the system. While users have generally expressed confidence in the PoDIUM platform, they are aware that it is not completely error-free and may occasionally experience minor faults. Issues such as temporary network instabilities may introduce hesitation or reduce confidence in specific features. This does not usually result in full rejection of the system, but it can affect how consistently users engage with assistance functions, especially those that require rapid or repeated compliance. Addressing this barrier requires more than improving technical performance (e.g., with multi-connectivity reliability), as it requires strengthening the user experience around reliability. Measures for this goal could include:

- Transparent communication of system limitations and post-event explanations or contextual messages, so users understand why certain faults occur and what they mean for safety, preventing misinterpretation and building confidence over time.
- Meaningful feedback loops, where the system clearly distinguishes between high-certainty and low-certainty information, allowing users to adjust their expectations instead of experiencing all information as equally urgent or equally questionable.
- Graceful degradation strategies, to ensure that when a component becomes unreliable (e.g., positioning or connectivity), the system shifts to a simplified mode that is clearly communicated to the user, rather than silently failing or generating misleading outputs.

Through these measures, trust can be reinforced not by promising error-free performance (which users already comprehend it is unrealistic), but by ensuring the system behaves in a transparent and interpretable way and is aligned with user expectations. This helps sustain confidence even when occasional technical faults inevitably occur.

PoDIUM implementation also faces challenges in ease of use and operational complexity, which arises from its architecture's own complexity. For instance, the instantaneous and context-specific nature of CCAM warnings creates high cognitive load for human interaction, especially in dynamic urban environments. The primary implication is that complex or poorly designed Human-Machine Interfaces (HMIs) might lead to driver frustration, and thereby its rejection. This should be addressed by prioritizing HMI design for low cognitive load, presenting pre-computed decision support rather than raw data. Furthermore, managing the entire distributed infrastructure demands specialized IT/OT expertise, increasing OpEx for road operators. Specialized training and user manuals are required to simplify the operational management of the complex, distributed PDI architecture for road authorities.

Finally, PoDIUM's PDI-enabled CCAM model faces growing competition from alternative and competing solutions. This includes the rapid advance of vehicle-centric sensor setups, which aim for vehicle autonomy based solely on onboard data, thus obviating the need for PDI. Furthermore, low-cost Over-the-Top (OTT) mobile network solutions for general traffic alters or crowd-sourced data provide an immediate and inexpensive alternative for consumers. This competition must be addressed by rigorously quantifying the unique values proposition of PDI-enabled cooperation: its ability to

provide validated, integrity-checked perception beyond line-of-sight and to enable complex, system-wide traffic optimization, which vehicle-only solutions cannot achieve.

Table 33 summarises the identified barriers to adoption, and how each of them can be addressed.

Table 33: Overview of barriers to adoption, and how they can be addressed.

Barrier description	How to address it
Regulatory and standardisation delays	Align with existing ETSI/ISO standards, comply with evolving EU frameworks, and provide pilot evidence to inform future updates.
Privacy and data protection	Apply privacy-by-design, anonymize data in real-time, ensure GDPR EU AI Act compliance.
Infrastructure readiness and deployment costs	Demonstrate ROI, promote public-private partnerships, and adopt modular/phased deployment using existing infrastructure.
User trust and perceived reliability	Communicate limitations clearly, provide contextual explanations, use feedback loops for uncertainty, and implement graceful degradation strategies.
Ease of Use	Design low-cognitive-load HMIs, provide training and documentation, and simplify operational workflows.
Alternatives / Competition	Quantify PDI-enabled value (beyond-line-of-sight perception, system-level optimization) and highlight interoperability and safety benefits.

5.4. Deployment readiness and scalability potential

The results from the three Living Labs indicate that the PoDIUM platform demonstrates a high level of functional maturity across diverse operational contexts such as urban intersections, VRU protection scenarios, emergency vehicle prioritisation, cross-border highway coordination, and highway tunnels. While the technological components remain at demonstration stage Technology Readiness Levels TRLs, several elements show readiness for near-term (on some occasions) deployment and further scaling.

Technical readiness

Across all Living Labs, users consistently rated PoDIUM solutions as useful, trustworthy, and supportive of enhanced safety, key indicators of readiness for pre-deployment trials. The multi-connectivity architecture and cooperative perception services functioned reliably during demonstrations, validating their applicability in real-world traffic management environments. Remaining gaps relate primarily to system robustness, interoperability across platforms, and the optimisation of user interfaces, particularly in complex urban environments.

Operational readiness

Demonstration feedback suggests that PoDIUM services can be integrated (following adaptations and modifications) into existing traffic management workflows with limited organisational disruption. Traffic managers in both urban and highway settings expressed readiness to incorporate the services,

provided clear operational guidelines and maintenance frameworks are in place. The demonstrated ability to support VRU visibility, priority vehicle movement, and tunnel risk management confirms high potential for uptake by public authorities and infrastructure operators.

Scalability potential

Scalability is supported by several design features of the PoDIUM platform:

- **Modular PDI architecture**, allowing components (e.g. cooperative perception, MEC-enabled processing, or new C-ITS messages) to be deployed independently or combined depending on local needs.
- **Interoperable data structures and cross-border operability**, strongly demonstrated in the Spanish UC3 corridor, showing that services can expand across administrative boundaries.
- **Compatibility with existing CCAM and C-ITS ecosystems**, enabling deployment in cities or motorways already investing in digital infrastructure.
- **Positive user acceptance**, with high intention to use and strong societal endorsement acting as key facilitators for broader adoption.

However, scaling across Europe requires addressing several barriers identified in Section 5.3: variability in digital infrastructure quality, alignment of national regulatory frameworks, long-term maintenance costs of PDI components, and persistent public concerns around data privacy and system reliability.

Overall assessment

Taking into consideration the public acceptance results, operational performance, and alignment with existing mobility systems, it can be suggested that PoDIUM could be well-positioned for future large-scale pilots and phased deployment. With continued technical refinement, close monitoring, and harmonisation with the European standards, the platform has strong potential to support consistent and scalable CCAM services across urban and highway networks.

5.5. Strategic implications for future deployment

The public acceptance results from the three Living Labs, Germany, Spain and Italy, jointly reveal a robust foundation for the development of CCAM services in Europe. Despite the differences in the local contexts and use cases, several converging patterns can be derived that have direct impact in the formulation of policies, standardisation efforts, the development of business strategies and public engagement frameworks.

5.5.1. Policy and Regulatory Implications

The consistently high levels of *Intention to Use* and *Perceived Usefulness* in all three Living Labs underscore the strong societal readiness for the deployment of CCAM. The participants of the survey acknowledged the clear public value of PoDIUM services, especially regarding the improvement of travel comfort and the inclusivity of vulnerable or disadvantaged groups. This confirms the direction of EU's policy agenda for CCAM, which promotes automation as a means for safer, more equitable and efficient mobility systems.

However, the findings also highlight the need for **policy harmonisation** at both National and cross-border levels. The results of Spanish cross-border case (UC3) reveal that users value continuity and reliability in multi-jurisdictional mobility systems but remain reluctant regarding the technical consistency. Thus, future CCAM regulation should focus not only on technological interoperability but

also on ensuring **regulatory coherence** across the Member States. This needs the establishment of shared performance baselines for data security, systems reliability and the protection of users' privacy.

In addition, the persistent trust-reliability gap that is observed in all Living Labs demonstrates that the **policy frameworks should provide priority to system's resilience over technical perfection**. Users exhibit pragmatic trust that is they do not expect operation without errors, but they would like guarantees that failures will not compromise safety. Consequently, deployment regulations should mandate transparent fail-safe protocols, redundancy measures and clear communication of system's limitations. Policymakers can enhance users' confidence through certification schemes for CCAM services, similar to the existing vehicle safety ratings.

5.5.2. Standardisation and Interoperability

The comparison of the LLs results reveal that public trust and ease of use are closely linked to **standardised service interfaces and consistent performance in all environments**. Participants in the urban Spanish use cases reported lower ease of use compared to highway scenarios, suggesting that human-machine interaction complexity significantly varies depending on the environment. These findings reinforce the need for **user-centred design standards** for CCAM interfaces, especially in dense urban networks where multiple actors, pedestrians, cyclists, emergency vehicles and automated systems, must interact fluidly.

Moreover, the moderate but constant **scores of privacy KPI** across the three sites highlight a common concern for the management of personal data. To support the large-scale deployment, **data governance standards** must ensure transparency. The adoption of common frameworks, such as the European initiative for Data Spaces, can facilitate the secure, anonymised information exchange, maintaining in parallel the compliance with GDPR principles. Technical standardisation must therefore be extended beyond communication protocols (e.g. 5G, ITS-G5) to include *ethical and privacy-by-design guidelines*, that make the value of data exchange explicit to end users.

Standardisation bodies (e.g. CEN, ISO, ETSI) are encouraged to incorporate findings like PoDIUM's "resilience over perfection" insight into future updates of CCAM related standards. Metrics should mirror public acceptance dimensions, trust, perceived usefulness and societal norm, as key KPIs along with purely technical benchmarks.

5.5.3. Business Strategy and Market Adoption

From a business perspective, high *Intention to Use and Social Norm* scores suggest an emerging **market opportunity for public-private partnerships** in CCAM services. The willingness of both individual users and professional operators (e.g. traffic managers) to integrate PoDIUM solutions shows that the multi-stakeholders business models can accelerate adoption. These could include subscription-based data services for traffic operators, shared infrastructure investment models or modular licensing for cooperative applications.

However, the relatively low *Reliability and Ease of Use* scores demonstrate that the business strategy for scaling up deployment should focus on **services maturity and operational transparency**. Enterprises should provide priority to user experience enhancement, especially in human-machine interaction phase, maintaining in parallel open communication about reliability thresholds and system limitations. Business value will not come from promising automation, but from guaranteeing **predictable performance and clear accountability mechanisms** when errors occur.

At the same time, the **moderate privacy confidence levels** indicate that commercial deployment should be accompanied by clear and accessible data management policies. Transparent consent

models and localised data storage options could enhance consumers' confidence and facilitate the compliance to the evolving digital legislation. Companies that enter this market should invest in **privacy literacy campaigns**, showing how users' data are anonymised, processed and used to improve safety outcomes.

5.5.4. Public Engagement, Training, and Communication

Perhaps the most decisive insight that stems from PoDIUM's surveys is the key role of **trust and understanding** in technology acceptance. While technical reliability remains an engineering challenge, *perceived trustworthiness* is largely shaped by social and communicative factors. This underscores the strategic need for **systematic public engagement programs** accompanying future CCAM rollouts.

Public awareness campaigns should go beyond generic narratives for the promotion of innovation to provide **transparent experience-based communication**. Demonstrations, visits to Living Labs and interactive simulations can contribute to the clarification/explanation of system operation and data use. Training programs for both professional operators (e.g. emergency responders, traffic authorities) and citizens will ensure informed participation and safer interaction with cooperative systems. Educational institutions and municipalities should participate in the co-development of such initiatives, integrating CCAM literacy into broader sustainability and digitalisation efforts.

In addition, the use of **community feedback loops** during pilot phases can lead to trust-building. By integrating users feedback when refining services, developers and policymakers indicate responsiveness and accountability which are key factors in sustaining public legitimacy. Communication campaigns must also demonstrate the **societal value of cooperation**, emphasising benefits such as accessibility for elder people or disabled persons, reduced congestion as well as environmental benefits.

5.5.5. Towards Scalable and Inclusive Deployment

Overall, PoDIUM survey findings reveal a public that is open, informed and optimistic regarding connected and automated mobility. To transform this acceptance into sustained adoption, future deployment strategies should be **multi-dimensional**, balancing technical progress with human factors, regulatory clarity and ethical governance.

The evidence supports a transition from prototype experimentation to **structured deployment frameworks** that are based on:

- Policy support for interoperability and resilience-based certification.
- Standardisation of user experience and privacy assurance mechanisms.
- Business models providing priority to transparency, reliability and co-created value.
- Continuous public engagement and education to maintain trust and inclusivity.

In conclusion, the cross-national results of PoDIUM offer not only proof of concept for cooperative mobility, but also a **roadmap for strategic deployment**. By integrating policy alignment, standardisation, commercial viability and public communication, future CCAM systems can evolve from isolated pilots to widespread, citizen-endorsed infrastructures that will re-define mobility across Europe.

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

The findings of this deliverable demonstrate that the PoDIUM platform and its associated PDI-enabled CCAM services achieve high levels of acceptance across diverse operational environments. Despite differences between urban and highway contexts, user groups, and national Living Labs, several common conclusions emerge:

Strong perceived value and willingness to adopt

Across all pilot sites, Perceived Usefulness was the strongest driver of acceptance, particularly in scenarios involving safety-critical cooperative manoeuvres and support for VRUs. Participants acknowledged the benefits of improved situational awareness, smoother traffic management, and increased comfort for both everyday users and disadvantaged groups. These high usefulness scores translate into a consistently positive Intention to Use, indicating readiness for real-world adoption.

Trust is well-established, but reliability expectations remain cautious

Users reported feeling safe within PoDIUM-supported demonstrations and expressed confidence in cooperative automation and infrastructure-supported guidance. However, the lower scores assigned to the “error-free” performance of systems highlight that trust does not necessarily imply belief in technical perfection. This “reliability paradox” appears across all Living Labs and suggests that deployment strategies should emphasise robustness, redundancy, and fault-tolerance rather than flawless operation.

Ease of use is context-dependent

The evaluation shows higher Ease of Use scores in highway demonstrations than in complex urban environments. Cooperative interactions involving emergency vehicles, VRUs, and multimodal flows require additional cognitive processing, which can influence perceived usability. These insights should inform future interface and HMI designs, ensuring simpler workflows in dense areas where user attention is already high.

Privacy concerns persist but do not undermine overall acceptance

Although most participants were willing to share certain data in exchange for safety benefits, privacy appeared as a consistent point of hesitation. This underlines the need for transparent data governance strategies, clear communication on what information is collected, and user-friendly consent mechanisms in future deployments.

PoDIUM's multi-connectivity and cooperative perception approach is validated

Feedback across all Living Labs confirms that combining redundant communication technologies, edge computing, and enhanced PDI features provides tangible benefits for safety and traffic efficiency. Users responded positively to the added situational awareness and overall coherence of the cooperative ecosystem.

Strong foundation for scalability and further deployment

The results collectively indicate that PoDIUM solutions have strong potential for scaling beyond the pilot environments. Positive user perceptions, combined with evidence from the impact assessment, demonstrate readiness for wider integration into urban and highway networks. Addressing reliability concerns, ensuring harmonised data protection practices, and refining user-oriented interfaces will further enhance adoption.